

Photoproduction of hydrogen by decamethylruthenocene combined with electrochemical recycling

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Abstract

The photo-induced hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) by decamethylruthenocene, $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$, is reported. The use of a metallocene to photo-produce hydrogen is presented as an alternative strategy to reduce protons without involving an additional photosensitizer. The mechanism was investigated by (spectro)electrochemical and spectroscopic (UV/vis and ^1H NMR) measurements and the photo-activated hydride involved was characterized spectroscopically. As a consequence of the light activation, the resulting $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]^+$ species was electrochemically regenerated *in situ* on a Fluorinated Tin Oxide (FTO) electrode surface with an onset potential 0.20 V more positive than that required for direct electrochemical evolution of hydrogen on Pt. A promising internal quantum yield of 25 % was obtained. To complete this investigation, optimal experimental conditions, especially the use of weakly coordinating solvent and counter ions, are discussed.

The development of simple and efficient methods to produce molecular hydrogen (H_2) is the focus of intense research. Various state-of-the-art multi-component artificial photo-systems to generate H_2 are currently under heavy scrutiny and generally consist of highly engineered catalyst, photosensitizer, electron mediator or relay combinations,^[1] fueled by sacrificial

electron donors (*e.g.*, triethylamine,^[2] triethanolamine,^[2b] benzyl-dihydronicotinamide,^[3] *etc.*). The latter irreversibly oxidize upon charge transfer and provide protons and electrons to the catalyst. Consequently, sacrificial systems consume a fuel to produce H₂ while electrochemical systems only consume electricity (that is now being increasingly produced in a sustainable manner). Indeed, the electrode can both accept and donate electrons. No irreversible reactions take place at this step, and the protons are supplied by the protons in solution.

Metallocenes appear as an attractive class of molecules capable of achieving the complex photo-generation of H₂ by themselves. Indeed, they are able to both reduce protons and undergo photo-activation. Therefore, these all-in-one molecules would offer an interesting alternative to state-of-the-art multi-component photosystems involving multiple electron transfer steps. Moreover, they are simple, easily synthesized molecules, with ligands and metal centers that may be tuned to obtain certain desired properties, such as tailored solubility, absorbance wavelength or redox potentials.

Recently, we demonstrated the possibility to produce H₂ in the dark using decamethylferrocene (Cp₂*Fe^(II); Cp* = C₅Me₅) as an electron donor in a biphasic system.^[4] Motivated by these early findings, we set out to explore the reactivity of other metallocenes as suitable electron donors. Interestingly, both osmocene (Cp₂Os^(II), Cp = C₅H₅)^[5] and decamethylsmocene (Cp₂*Os^(II))^[6] demonstrated capabilities to produce H₂ upon light irradiation. Other works have proposed the use of a single molecule to achieve the photo-generation of H₂. For example, Cole-Hamilton^[7] reported a platinum phosphine compound, while both Miller^[8] and Gray^[9] used iridium chloride complexes.

Herein, we report Cp₂*Ru^(II) as the first metallocene capable of performing the photo-generation of H₂ by itself with subsequent regeneration of the oxidized decamethylruthenocenium cation ([Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺) at a more positive potential than that of proton reduction. The photo-electrocatalytic activity of Cp₂*Ru^(II) towards the H₂ evolution reaction (HER) was proven by electrochemical studies. The general mechanism leading to H₂ evolution was studied using (spectro)electrochemistry and spectroscopy (UV/vis, ¹H NMR). This study represents significant progress in the application of light-driven electrochemically reversible metallocenes as key elements in an attractive, viable new artificial photosystem towards water-splitting applications.

Photo-electrocatalytic H₂ generation by Cp₂*Ru^(II) was achieved directly using tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate diethyletherate acid ([H(OEt₂)₂]TB) as the source of proton

in 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), prepared as described in Section 1 of the Supporting Information (SI). All experiments were performed under inert conditions in a glove box. $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ does not need a reductive activation step to be protonated. Thus, in acidified organic solutions, $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ is spontaneously converted to $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{H})]^+$ in the dark as described by eq. (1):

The protonation at the metal to form the cationic hydride in the dark was monitored by ^1H NMR spectroscopy and UV/vis spectroscopy (see Section 2, SI)

Earlier studies provided key clues to predict the behavior of photo-activated $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{H})]^+$ during H_2 evolution.^[10] In particular, it has been assumed that the cationic $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]^+$ species is generated *in situ* during irradiation of $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{H})]^+$ in acidified organic solutions (Figure 1). The identification and characterization of $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]^+$ has been obstructed in previous studies due to its high instability and very short life time, and $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]^+$ was assumed to convert rapidly to $[\text{Cp}^*\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_4\text{CH}_2)]^+$.^[10a-d] Therefore, we focused our efforts on optimizing the right conditions to stabilize the transient $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]^+$ species long enough to allow its electrochemical regeneration and thus obtain a catalytic generation of H_2 *via* a catalytic Electrochemical, Chemical, Chemical mechanism (ECC' mechanism)^[11] described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Electrochemical recycling of $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ *via* an Electrochemical, Chemical, Chemical (ECC') mechanism incorporating light-activated H_2 evolution.

The influence of solvents and supporting electrolytes on the electrochemical behavior of $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ are discussed in more detail in Section 3 of the SI. Several studies reporting the formation of $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{M}^{\text{III}}]^+$ in the presence of a nucleophilic counter anion highlight the instability of the oxidized metallocenes under these experimental conditions.^[10a, 12] Indeed,

poorly stabilized $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{M}^{(\text{III})}]^+$ may oxidize a second time to form breakdown products (see Section 3, SI). Furthermore, breakdown of $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{M}^{(\text{III})}]^+$ is accelerated in the presence of coordinating solvents.^[10b, 13] In this work, we successfully prepared reasonably stable $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{III})}]^+$ species (at least on the time-scale of the electrolysis experiments) by utilizing the soft tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate counter anion in DCE, and spectroelectrochemically characterized the production of the $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{III})}]^+$ species (see Figure S5, Section 3, SI for further details).

The electrochemical behavior of $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ was further characterized by cyclic voltammetry (CV). CVs of $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ in the absence of acid clearly show an oxidation and a reduction peak for the $\text{Ru}^{(\text{III})}/\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ redox process with a formal potential of 0.75 V *versus* the aqueous standard hydrogen electrode (SHE) (Section 4, SI). The voltammetry after the addition of acid in excess did not show any electrochemical activity inside the potential window due to the production of the protonated $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ species ($[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{IV})}(\text{H})]^+$). Subsequently, upon light illumination through the FTO working electrode using an LED light source at $\lambda = 365$ nm, a clear catalytic current corresponding to the reduction of the photogenerated $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{III})}]^+$ to $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ appeared with an onset potential slightly positive of the $[\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{III})}]^+/\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ redox transition (Figure 2(A), green solid line). No return peak was observed suggesting a fast protonation of the $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$. As shown in Figure 2(A), photo-electrocatalysis with $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ on an FTO electrode surface takes place at a potential 0.20 V higher (more positive) than direct electrocatalysis on the Pt electrode surface. H_2 evolution on Pt should be a bench-mark to compare with all systems involving photoinduced electron transfer and regeneration of some species at the electrode. The comparison with Pt highlights the more favorable regeneration of $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{(\text{II})}$ towards water splitting applications.

Figure 2. (A) CV of 4 mM [H(OEt₂)₂]TB in DCE with 0.1 M TBAPF₆ supporting electrolyte without (FTO – solid blue and Pt – dashed blue lines) or with 1 mM Cp₂*Ru^(II) (green CVs with and without illumination). Scan rate 5 mV·s⁻¹. (B) CPE of the same solution of 1 mM Cp₂*Ru^(II) and excess [H(OEt₂)₂]TB in DCE with 0.1 M TBAPF₆ as supporting electrolyte on an FTO electrode at 0.50 V vs. SHE with the LED illumination switched periodically on (white) and off (grey). The full CPE experimental setup is illustrated in the SI. (C) Identical conditions as (B), the illumination is switched on for 10 h and H₂ production was compared with or without applying a potential to the FTO electrode. The experiment was repeated 3 times (see Section 5, SI).

The appearance of the reductive catalytic current in the presence of organic protons, Cp₂*Ru^(II) and light was also confirmed by constant potential electrolysis (CPE) performed at 0.50 V vs. SHE (Figure 2(B) and Section 4, SI). Initially, prior to illumination, almost no current apart from the double-layer charging was observed, in agreement with the CVs generated under these conditions in Figure 2(A). Upon illumination, Cp₂*Ru^(II) was

immediately oxidized (and H₂ evolved, as shown by head-space analysis with gas chromatography, Section 5, SI) causing the negative current to quickly increase in magnitude due to the regeneration of [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ species at the FTO electrode surface. When the LED was switched off, the current immediately began to drop with the disappearance of the [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ species in the vicinity of the FTO electrode on conversion to Cp₂*Ru^(II) and subsequent immediate protonation by [H(OEt)₂]₂TB.

The solution turned from colorless to pink after exposure to the LED light. Upon illumination, [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ was also produced in the bulk solution, much too far from the electrode surface to be reduced back to Cp₂*Ru^(II) on the timescale of the experiment. Subsequent analysis by UV/vis spectroscopy revealed a characteristic absorbance band at 500 nm (see Section 5, Figure S12, SI), identified as the [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ species (Figure S5, Section 3, SI).

The CPE experiment was repeated overnight (i) without applying a potential and (ii) applying a constant potential of 0.50 V vs. SHE (see Figure 2(C), and Section 5, SI). More H₂ was evolved for the latter confirming the regeneration of the [Cp₂*Ru^(IV)(H)]⁺ species and its ability to participate once again in the photo-driven HER.

The quantum yield (QY) for the photo-electrocatalytic generation of H₂ from an acidified organic solution of Cp₂*Ru^(II) is defined as $QY = 2n_{H_2} / n_{hv} = n[Cp_2^*Ru^{(III)}]^+ / n_{hv}$. The QY was determined by quantifying the amount of [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ evolved from a 2 mM Cp₂*Ru^(II) solution in DCE with protons in excess (4 mM) at a given photon flux by UV/vis spectroscopy (Figure S13, Section 6, SI). Details of the calculations are provided in Section 6, SI. An internal QY of 25 % was achieved. Considering the transmittance spectrum of the FTO electrode (see Figure S14, Section 6, SI) the production rate of [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ was recalculated and a theoretical maximum QY of 17 % was determined. Importantly, by following the appearance of [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ spectroscopically to determine the QY, overestimations by incorporation of any H₂ that may have been produced by degradation of the catalyst were avoided.

The influence of the excitation wavelength was investigated to characterize the transition involved in the photo-reaction. Titration by UV/vis spectroscopy revealed the spectral features of [Cp₂*Ru^(IV)(H)]⁺ with a main absorption band at 243 nm (Figure S3, Section 2, SI). The maximum production of H₂ and [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ observed at 243 nm (see Figure S15, Section 7, SI) firmly proved the involvement of electronically excited [Cp₂*Ru^(IV)(H)]⁺ in the photoreaction. It also corroborates the photoactivity of [Cp₂*Ru^(IV)(H)]⁺ in the near-UV with a

lower but reasonable QY. The absorption spectrum computed at the TD- ω B97X-D level shows that the main band is dominated by one transition which induces an electronic enrichment on the hydride position after excitation (Section 7, SI).

In summary, we have demonstrated the use of a single molecule, Cp₂*Ru^(II), that is able to photo-electrochemically generate H₂ with an internal quantum yield of 25 %. More importantly, the resulting [Cp₂*Ru^(III)]⁺ can be electrochemically regenerated with an onset potential 200 mV more positive than for the direct electrochemical reduction of protons on a Pt electrode. ¹H NMR and (spectro)electrochemical studies provided guidelines to understand the mechanism. Looking beyond Cp₂*Ru^(II), we believe that the development of metallocene catalysts for H₂ photo-production could open an interesting new research avenue. Coupled with a light driven catalyst for water oxidation, such as bismuth vanadate,^[14] it has the potential to significantly impact the field of water-splitting.

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A $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ single molecule photogenerated hydrogen with an internal quantum yield of 25%. $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ was electrochemically regenerated in situ and spectroscopic studies enabled deconvolution of the operating reaction mechanism. Combined with electrochemical recycling, metallocene electron donors such as $\text{Cp}_2^*\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ could work in tandem with a water oxidation catalyst to photoproduce H_2 from water.